

Quantum Key Distribution: Introduction, Protocols and Current Challenges

Astha Yadav

4th Year, B.Sc. Physics Honors

Physics Department - Kirori Mal College, University of Delhi

Abstract

As quantum computing threatens the foundations of classical asymmetric cryptography, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) has been heralded as a vital alternative for unconditional security. This article reviews the theoretical framework of QKD, compares dominant protocols such as BB84 and E91, and evaluates the hurdles limiting their widespread viability. Key implementation challenges, ranging from transmission distance limits to hardware-specific side-channel attacks, are discussed. The review highlights that the future of the Quantum Internet depends not only on theoretical protocols but on overcoming the practical security and infrastructure gaps currently preventing widespread adoption.

Keywords: Quantum Key Distribution, QKD Security, Quantum Cryptography, Quantum Communication, Quantum Computing

Abbreviations:

QKD: Quantum Key Distribution

QBER: Quantum Bit Error Rate

OTP: One Time Pad

1 Introduction

Quantum Key Distribution protocols are an application of Quantum Cryptography. To know why it is needed, an introduction to cryptography and its need is significant.

1.1 Cryptography and the need for a Key

[1] Cryptography is concerned with information security, basing itself on theoretical mathematics to ensure the security of information. Reliable communication and dissemination of information via the internet is a significant advancement in modern society. Information is only useful if its from a legitimate source, but bad actors exist who make efforts to corrupt such information for their own benefit. This threat is augmented in exchange of sensitive information like military communication. How then, do we ensure the secure transmission and authenticity of information? The answer lies within cryptography.

Simply put, the information to be shared is changed to a 'jumbled' form, which can only be 'un-jumbled' with a 'key'. In technical terms the information i.e. 'plaintext', is first encoded into bits, then certain algorithms operate on the bit-string. The process is called **encryption**. These algorithms contain functions that take both the plaintext and another bit-string called the 'key'. The changed form, which is transmitted via channels, is called 'ciphertext'. A ciphertext if decoded looks like gibberish text that does not relay any information about the original text. The receiver converts ciphertext back to plaintext using the key, and this is called **decryption**.

1.1.1 Mathematical Formalism

Let's define a cryptographic system; it will be defined using this group: $(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{D})$, where:

- \mathcal{M} is the set of all possible plaintexts or original data
- \mathcal{C} represents the set of all possible ciphertexts
- \mathcal{K} represents the keyspace (from where we'll get our binary key)
- \mathcal{E} is the encryption function i.e. $E_k : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$.
- \mathcal{D} is the decryption function $D_k : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$.

A cipher uses the dual functions and the spaces. In modern day computing the plaintext m , ciphertext c and key k all would be binary. The encryption function takes in both m and k as inputs and outputs c .

The decryption function takes c and k as inputs and outputs m . Without the key k , we can't retrieve the original message.

1.1.2 Example: One Time Pad

One time Pad is one of the simplest encryption schemes which uses bitwise Exclusive-OR (XOR) operation. Given a plaintext m and a secret key k of equal length, the ciphertext c can be obtained by $c = m \oplus k$. To decrypt, the recipient XORs the ciphertext with the same key: $c \oplus k = (m \oplus k) \oplus k = m$.

Let m be "a", decoding using ASCII - 'a' in ASCII is 97 i.e. 01100001 in bits.

Let k be 10101010.

$$\begin{array}{r} 01100001 \text{ (plaintext)} \\ \oplus 10101010 \text{ (key)} \\ \hline 11001011 \text{ (ciphertext)} \end{array}$$

Now to decode the ciphertext,

$$\begin{array}{r} 11001011 \text{ (ciphertext)} \\ \oplus 10101010 \text{ (key)} \\ \hline 01100001 \end{array}$$

As we can see 01100001 is indeed our original plaintext, i.e. 'a'. This scheme is called the One Time Pad (OTP). It has perfect secrecy[2] but it's major drawback is that the key needs to be as big as the plaintext.

1.1.3 Two Major Methods

Modern communication relies on two primary architectures of cryptography.

Symmetric-key cryptography where both parties use a secret key - only known to each other to encrypt their data and send it to each other using a public channel. If a bad actor tried to intercept the messages, they'd only get gibberish, unless they have the key k .

$$c = E(m, k) \implies m = D(c, k) \quad (1)$$

The OTP is an example of symmetric encryption. The major drawback is key-distribution. The key needs to be truly randomly generated and as long as message (plaintext) and to be secretly transmitted. We are better off directly transmitting the message than the key if we find such a secure channel. This highlights the 'Key Distribution Problem'—the paradox of needing a secure channel to establish a secure channel. Even if we use pseudo-random generator functions and a smaller truly random seed, key distribution remains a main concern.

Asymmetric-key cryptography or Public Key Cryptography addresses this by utilizing a mathematically linked key pair (k_{pub}, k_{priv}) . The public key is available for everyone to encrypt

message, but while decryption is strictly reserved for the holder of the private key:

$$c = E(m, k_{pub}) \quad \text{and} \quad m = D(c, k_{priv}) \quad (2)$$

Systems using this include RSA and Elliptic Curve Cryptography. They rely on the mathematical hardness of the problem like integer factorization and discrete logarithms etc. to encrypt the message, which can only be accessed through private key. If someone tried to run a brute force attack i.e. run through all possible key iterations to get the correct one, they would take exponential time.

1.2 Quantum Computers affecting Cryptography

The security of our current digital infrastructure is built on the assumption that some mathematical problems are practically impossible to solve in a reasonable time, unless we have the key. However, the advent of **Quantum Computers** has challenged this. [3]

In 1994, Peter Shor developed a quantum algorithm capable of factoring large integers in polynomial time. For a classical computer, factoring a 2048-bit RSA key is estimated to take billions of years; a sufficiently powerful quantum computer could theoretically achieve this in hours. This is expressed by the complexity shift:[4]

- **Classical Complexity:** $O(\exp(n^{1/3}(\log n)^{2/3}))$
- **Quantum Complexity (Shor's):** $O(n^2 \log n \log \log n)$

1.3 Quantum Cryptography

Quantum Cryptography ensures security against all classical and quantum attacks due to the physical properties involved[5][6]. It relies on the fundamental laws of quantum physics. Information is encoded in quantum states for example the polarization of photons. Quantum properties of **superposition**, **entanglement**, **no-cloning theorem** and **the observer effect** are leveraged in quantum cryptography applications.

- **Superposition** allows a quantum system to exist in multiple states simultaneously until measured, enabling a single photon to represent complex combinations of basis states.
- **Entanglement** describes a unique correlation where two particles are linked in a manner that the quantum state of one instantaneously influences the other, regardless of how large the distance is[7].
- **No-Cloning Theorem** forbids the creation of an identical copy of an unknown quantum state[8].

- **Observer Effect** ensures that any attempt to observe or measure the quantum carrier will inevitably change the state of the system.

The applications of quantum cryptography include Quantum Random Number Generators (QRNGs), Quantum Hash Functions, Quantum Digital Signatures, and the major one - Quantum Key Distribution Protocols.

2 QKD Protocols

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) refers to the distribution of the key for symmetric encryption to sender and recipient through protocols where security is assured due to quantum properties of transmitted particles. It is proven to be 'unconditionally secure' [9]. There's two types of Quantum Public Key Cryptography (QPKC). The QPKC1 is a QKD where the key is still composed of binary bits. QPKC Class 2 is made up of quantum qubits[10]. No-cloning theorem plays major role in QKD as the shared state can't be cloned[8]. A key is securely transmitted which can be used for symmetric encryption or used along with other classically secure algorithms like AES or 3DES[11].

The first QKD protocol was introduced by Bennett and Brassard in 1984. Many QKD protocols have been developed over the years, many being a modification to BB84. The other major QKD protocol was E91 which is entanglement based. Both are discussed below.

2.1 BB84 Protocol

Introduced by Bennett and Brassard in 1984[6]. The sender called Alice and the recipient called Bob are connected through an ideal secure lossless quantum channel and a public classical channel through which there can be passive eavesdroppers. The basic idea is that an observer can't intercept the signal and copy it without the sender-receiver knowing. Due to observer's effect and no-cloning theorem - mentioned before.

The goal is to transmit a key bit-string. The bit-string is encoded into photon polarizations. Polarization of light is characterized by the direction of vibration of electric field, perpendicular to its propagation direction. For a single photon polarization can be described in a two dimensional Hilbert space. Here, four polarization directions will be used: the vertical, horizontal, diagonal and anti-diagonal directions in two bases X (diagonal) and Z (rectilinear).

The Rectilinear Basis (Z): Used to encode bits in the vertical $|\uparrow\rangle = |1\rangle$ or horizontal $|\rightarrow\rangle = |0\rangle$ state.

The Diagonal Basis (X): Used to encode bits in the $|\nearrow\rangle$ or $|\searrow\rangle$ states, where [12]:

$$|\nearrow\rangle = \frac{|\rightarrow\rangle + |\uparrow\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = |+\rangle \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Quantum and Classical Channels in BB84[13]

$$|\searrow\rangle = \frac{|\rightarrow\rangle - |\uparrow\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = |-\rangle \quad (4)$$

The protocol in action:

- Alice chooses between Z and X basis on random.
- Alice chooses between 0 and 1 on random.
- Alice sends out a single photon corresponding to the basis and state through a quantum channel.
- Bob chooses a random basis and measures the incoming photon.
- This process is repeated thousands of times usually, till they have a reasonable amount of bits.
- Now they shift to a classical public channel.
- They share the bases that they used. They keep the bits for when the bases matched, and discard when they didn't. This is called **sifting**.
- To check that there wasn't an eavesdropper, they compare a reasonable amount of bits from the sifted string.
- Some level of noise is expected so we have a threshold called measured using QBER - Quantum Bit Error Rate.
- Generally QBER below 11% is accepted as secure. [14]. If it is above 11%, the session is aborted.

Table 1: BB84 Polarization Encoding Scheme

Basis	Rectilinear (Z)		Diagonal (X)	
Binary Value	0	1	0	1
Photon State	$ 0\rangle$ (\uparrow)	$ 1\rangle$ (\rightarrow)	$ +\rangle$ (\nearrow)	$ -\rangle$ (\searrow)

n	A's bit	A's basis	A's qubit	B's basis	B's qubit	B's bit	Key
1	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	0	0
2	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle / -\rangle$	0/1	
3	1	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	1	1
4	0	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle / 1\rangle$	0/1	
5	1	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	1	1
6	1	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	1	1
7	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle / -\rangle$	0/1	
8	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	0	0

Figure 2: Sifted Key[13]

n	A's bit	A's basis	A's qubit	E's basis	E's qubit	B's basis	B's qubit	B's bit	Key
1	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	0	0
2	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	1	
3	1	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle$	0	0
4	0	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	1	
5	1	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	1	1
6	1	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 1\rangle$	1	1
7	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ -\rangle$	1	
8	0	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_x	$ +\rangle$	\mathcal{B}_z	$ 0\rangle$	0	0

Figure 3: BB84 in presence of an eavesdropper[13]

As illustrated in Figure 2, in the absence of an eavesdropper and following the discard of inconsistent bases, Alice and Bob undergo the sifting process to extract the raw key. While a small bit-string is shown here for illustration, practical QKD implementations typically require block sizes on the order of 10^4 to 10^6 bits. This large volume is necessary to ensure the efficacy of Privacy Amplification protocols [15].

Figure 3 displays the protocol in presence of Eavesdropper "Eve". In this case, the security relies on statistical detection. Eve chooses a random basis, measures each qubit and resends it to Bob - another qubit in the state corresponding to her measurement. This is termed as "intercept-resend strategy". As she chooses the basis randomly, in 50% of instances, she may choose correctly and remain undetected; however, in the remaining 50%, she will inevitably use an incompatible basis, introducing a state transformation that Bob will measure incorrectly. On average, this intervention introduces a 25% Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER) in the sifted key. By processing large bit-strings, Alice and Bob can statistically distinguish this error rate from natural channel noise, thereby confirming the presence of an intruder [5]."

QBER is important as it is used to determine the next steps in the protocol. Alice and Bob compare a random subset of the sifted bits. According to the Shor-Preskill security proof, if the QBER remains below the theoretical threshold of approximately 11%, the protocol proceeds

to error correction and privacy amplification. [14]. However, if the error rate exceeds this threshold, the system concludes that the information leaked to an eavesdropper is too high to be eliminated; the current session is subsequently aborted, the bits are discarded, and a new transmission is initiated.

Error Correction or Information Reconciliation: QBER can be introduced due to noise in the physical channel along with Eve’s interventions and introduce a discrepancy in bits of the key. Error correction aims to reconcile these discrepancies using parity bits of small blocks of their key. These are communicated classically and protocols like Cascade or Winnow are used. These allow Bob to identify and flip erroneous bits by comparing the parities. This exchange is designed to be ”leakage-resilient” and ensures that the amount of information revealed to an eavesdropper during the error-correction stage is minimized [16].

Privacy Amplification: Alice and Bob assume the possibility that eavesdropper (Eve) might have gotten lucky and gained partial information. They apply a Universal Hash Function, which maps the long bit-string into a shorter, highly secure one. Mathematically, this reduces Eve’s maximum possible information to an exponentially small value, effectively ”amplifying” the privacy of the remaining bits [17].

Other BB84 based schemes have been developed like B92 [18] created by BB84 coauthor Bennett, SARG04 [19], and the Six-State Protocol [20].

While BB84 is effective, it requires Alice to have a trusted source and a perfectly random number generator. If a bad actor can predict the basis choices the security is compromised as Alice and Bob would have no way of knowing about Eve. The next major protocol - E91 protocol removes the need for a trusted source. By using entanglement, the randomness is inherent to the quantum system itself, and security can be verified using a statistical test known as a Bell Test based on Bell’s Inequality[21].

2.2 E91 Protocol (Entanglement-based QKD)

Proposed by Artur Ekert in 1991, this protocol shifts foundation for security from state preparation to the violation of **Bell’s Inequality** [7]. Unlike BB84, E91 utilizes a central source that distributes entangled photon pairs (typically EPR pairs) to both Alice and Bob. If the states are maximally entangled, they have guaranteed security. The entanglement is measured through a CHSH inequality test [22].

$$S = E(A_1, B_1) - E(A_1, B_3) + E(A_3, B_1) + E(A_3, B_3) \quad (5)$$

If $S = 2\sqrt{2}$, then the states are maximally entangled and are secure [23].

Steps of the Protocol:

- **Distribution:** A central source generates entangled pairs; one qubit is sent to Alice and

Figure 4: E-91 Protocol: Distribution of Pairs[24]

Figure 5: E-91 Protocol: Alice and Bob measure in three bases at random[25]

the other to Bob as seen in Figure 4. The source of entanglement can be Eve herself since she cannot know anything about the generated key; the key is generated when the measurement is made by Alice and Bob.

- **Measurement:** Both parties choose from three different measurement bases at random. To maximize the Bell violation ($S = 2\sqrt{2}$), Bob's bases (B_1, B_2, B_3) are typically rotated by 22.5° relative to Alice's (A_1, A_2, A_3):

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= 0^\circ (Z) & B_1 &= 22.5^\circ \\ A_2 &= 45^\circ \left(\frac{Z + X}{\sqrt{2}} \right) & B_2 &= 67.5^\circ \\ A_3 &= 90^\circ (X) & B_3 &= 112.5^\circ \end{aligned}$$

- **Sifting:** Alice and Bob publicly announce their basis choices. Instances where they used the same basis are used to form the **Raw Key**. This is where the key is actually "generated".
- **Bell Test:** Instances where they used *different* bases are used to test for the violation of the **CHSH inequality** [21].
- **Verification:** If the calculated correlation value $S \approx 2\sqrt{2}$, the entanglement is confirmed. If $S \leq 2$, it indicates the entanglement has been broken, likely due to an intercept-resend attack or environmental decoherence. The session is then aborted.

In case of E-91 too, we need to establish an QBER threshold for noise. Noise will be introduced due to the fact that perfectly correlated pairs can't be practically generated, by inherent noise in the transmission medium and by possible interventions by Eve. Below the threshold, given we have sufficient entanglement, the same steps are performed as BB84: **Information Reconciliation** and **Privacy Amplification** [7].

2.3 BB84 vs E-91

In BB84, the secret bits and basis choices may be pre-determined and stored at the sender's side; if an adversary compromises Alice's random number generator or storage, the entire system's security is nullified. Whereas in E-91 the key is generated only when Alice and Bob do the measurement. Hence, E91 can be proven unconditionally secure even in the presence of an untrusted source, provided maximal entanglement is verified [26].

Despite these theoretical advantages, BB84 remains more prominent in practical network testbeds due to its lower implementation complexity. E91 is currently more restricted in multi-node environments and is often limited to single-link configurations. Notably, the most significant distance achieved using an entanglement-based protocol was demonstrated via satellite-to-ground links, reaching over 1,120 km [27].

3 Current Challenges

Despite the theoretical advantage, QKD protocols suffer from practical implementation problems which are the roadblock to realizing the secure Quantum Networks and Quantum Internet. These challenges range from the physics of the fiber itself to the imperfections of the hardware used to detect photons. In this section, discuss physical transmission limits and security concerns of QKD.

3.1 Transmission Limit: Signal Attenuation and the PLOB Bound

The security of QKD protocols is ensured because quantum states cannot be copied. But this becomes a challenge in realizing single-link QKD protocols to a network. In the classical internet, a "packet" of information travels through several "repeaters" or "routers" that amplify the signal to ensure it reaches its destination. Because quantum signals cannot be amplified without collapsing their state, they suffer from exponential signal loss (attenuation) within optical fibers [28].

This limitation is quantified using the **PLOB Bound** (named after Pirandola, Laurenza, Ottaviani, and Banchi) and it is used to define the fundamental upper limit of the secret key rate. This bound establishes the maximum possible capacity of a lossy quantum channel, regardless

of the protocol implemented [29]. For a channel with transmittivity η (the probability of a photon not being lost), the secret key capacity K is bounded by:

$$K \leq -\log_2(1 - \eta) \quad (6)$$

As the distance increases, η decreases, causing the secret key rate to drop. This rate-loss means that for any point-to-point fiber link, there is a physical distance beyond which key generation becomes impossible. Surpassing this limit requires the development of quantum repeaters or the use of satellite-based free-space links to bypass fiber-optic attenuation.

3.2 Security Challenges: Theoretical and Practical

While the protocols discussed are mathematically secure, physical implementations introduce vulnerabilities that an eavesdropper (Eve) can exploit. These challenges are generally categorized into attacks on the quantum protocol itself (the "main" channel) and attacks on the physical hardware (side-channels) [30].

3.2.1 Protocol-Level Attacks (The Main Channel)

These attacks target the fundamental quantum communication process [31]. They are categorised based on Eve's capabilities:

- **Individual Attacks:** Eve interacts with each qubit independently and performs measurements to gain information.
- **Collective Attacks:** Eve interacts with each qubit but stores her own ancilla states in a quantum memory, measuring them together after the sifting process to maximize her information gain.
- **Coherent Attacks:** The most powerful theoretical category where Eve targets the entire sequence of qubits as a single entangled system. A protocol proven secure against coherent attacks is considered "unconditionally secure" [31].

3.2.2 Implementation and Side-Channel Attacks

A "side-channel" attack exploits information that inadvertently leaks from physical components (lasers, fibers, and detectors) rather than the protocol logic[30]. These can also be classified as attacks on source or attacks on destination. Some of the examples include:

- **Photon Number Splitting (PNS):** Since practical lasers often emit multi-photon pulses instead of single photons, as a single photon has the possibility to get lost or absorbed, Eve can siphon off one of the many photons without Alice or Bob knowing. This allows her to gain key information without increasing the QBER and thus escaping detection.

- **Detector Control Attack:** This is a powerful attack type that has been shown to compromise many practical QKD systems [32]. These attacks can be detector-blinding, where Eve illuminates bright light to control detectors; detector-after-gate or detector-superlinear attack.
- **Information Leakage:** These include attacks like **Differential Power Analysis (DPA)** or timing attacks, where Eve monitors the power consumption or processing time of Alice or Bob’s devices to infer secret key material [30].

There’s still many challenges being worked upon in QKD to realize wider implementation. There has been rejection and criticism of the technology and pushback against implementation by national security agencies and individual researchers who question the practicality and overall necessity of the infrastructure [11, 3, 33].

4 Conclusion

Quantum Key Distribution offer unconditional security which, could lead to an era of significant reduction in information leakage. Although QKD systems have existed for decades and represent a relatively mature technology, their application remains largely confined to experimental testbeds, scientific research, or highly niche, singular use cases. The transition of QKD into common, widespread use remains a work in progress.

It faces significant challenges to its wider implementation most notably the transmission limits inherent to point-to-point systems. Overcoming these constraints requires the development of functional quantum repeaters to evolve from simple links into true quantum networks. Further, practical security vulnerabilities and various ”side-channel” attacks continue to pose challenges. While QKD has faced criticism regarding these limitations, it is best to withhold final conclusions until large-scale QKD networks are fully realized in real-world environments and evaluated through extended practical usage and security checks.

Disclosure Statement

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